

1 **Selective solid-phase extraction of organophosphorus pesticides and their oxon-**
2 **derivatives from water samples using molecularly imprinted polymer followed by**
3 **HPLC-UV**

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26 **Abstract**

27 A molecularly imprinted polymer was synthesized and characterized to be used as
28 solid-phase extraction sorbent for simultaneous chlorpyrifos and diazinon and their
29 oxon derivatives. Several imprinted polymers were prepared and evaluated in a
30 retention study of these analytes compared with a non-printed polymer. Several
31 parameters affecting the extraction of imprinted polymer such as washing solvent,
32 composition and volume of the eluting solvent and sample volume, were also
33 investigated. Under the optimum conditions, the developed method provided
34 satisfactory limits of detection ranging between $0.07 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ to $0.12 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and the
35 material showed an excellent reusability (> 50 reuses). The method was applied to the
36 extraction and preconcentration of these analytes in water samples. The average
37 recoveries ranged from 79 ± 6 to 104 ± 3 %.

38

39 **Keywords:** molecularly imprinted polymer; environmental water samples; pollutants;
40 SPE; organophosphorus pesticides; pesticides-oxon.

41

42 **1. Introduction**

43 Organophosphorus pesticides (OPPs) are widely used compounds in pest control.
44 These pesticides involve not only an environmental risk, due to their low
45 biodegradability, but they also can affect the human health. Indeed, they are found to
46 be cytotoxic, genotoxic and mutagenic [1] due to the inhibition of the
47 acetylcholinesterase [2]. Due to their extensive use, several of these pesticides end-up
48 in surface and ground waters. In addition, most pesticides in surface water are not
49 removed or transformed during physical-chemical treatment in sewage water plants.
50 For instance, it has been reported that during chlorination process in the water
51 purification process, the phosphorothioate group (P=S) can be oxidized to the
52 phosphorus oxygen double bond (P=O), thus forming their corresponding oxon forms
53 [3]. These oxons are relatively persistent by chlorination and their toxicity have
54 showed to be higher than their parent compounds [4].

55 The most frequently analytical techniques used to determine traces of these pesticides
56 are based on chromatographic separation (gas chromatography (GC) or liquid
57 chromatography (LC)) coupled to mass spectrometry (MS) detection. Despite of the
58 use of these sophisticated techniques, the proposed methods for OPP quantitation still
59 requires of extraction and preconcentration steps [5-9]. In this sense, different sample
60 preparation techniques such as dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction (DLLME)
61 [10], stir bar sorptive extraction (SBSE) [11], solid-phase microextraction (SPME)
62 [12] as well as the conventional solid-phase extraction (SPE) (with C18-based
63 material) [13] and its magnetic version [14] have been employed for the extraction of
64 these pollutants from water samples. However, poor selectivity is the common
65 drawback present in all these extraction techniques. To overcome this disadvantage,
66 there is a considerable interest in developing new selective materials with molecular

67 recognition mechanism to isolate these pollutants from complex environmental
68 matrices. In this sense, molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) are promising
69 polymeric sorbents that can exhibit high affinity and selectivity towards a particular
70 analyte or a group of structurally related compounds [15].

71 Attending to the use of MIP, several authors have been extensively explored their
72 application as selective phases for the extraction of OPPs. MIPs has been prepared in
73 SPE cartridges [16, 17, 18, 19, 20] or other formats including dispersive SPE [21, 22,
74 23], matrix solid-phase dispersion [24, 25] and also extended to SBSE [26] or SPME
75 [27, 28]. However, these pretreatment methodologies have not been applied for
76 simultaneous extraction of OPPs and their oxon forms, which are even more
77 hazardous.

78 The aim of this work was the synthesis of a MIP for OPPs (chlorpyrifos and diazinon)
79 and their corresponding oxon metabolites and its application as SPE sorbent in real
80 water samples. For this purpose, the synthesis of several imprinted polymers was done
81 by varying the nature of the template to achieve the optimal retention of target
82 analytes. The selected MIP was investigated in detail to accomplish the best extraction
83 performance for all target compounds. Several analytical features of the SPE phase
84 such as adsorption capacity, breakthrough volume and reusability were established.
85 The optimal conditions of the method were applied to quantify OPPs and their oxon
86 derivatives in environmental aqueous samples. To our knowledge, it is the first
87 application of MIP for simultaneous determination of OPPs and their oxon forms (with
88 different polarities) followed by HPLC-UV analysis that could be interesting to assure
89 the human safety and guarantee an environmental control.

90

91 **2. Experimental**

92 *2.1. Materials and reagents*

93 Methacrylic acid (MAA), ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (EGDMA), 2,2'-azobis-
94 isobutyronitrile (AIBN), sodium phosphate salts were obtained from Sigma–Aldrich
95 (Barcelona, Spain). Chlorpyrifos (O,O-diethyl-O[3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinyl]
96 phosphorothioate, 99.5%), Chlorpyrifos-oxon (O,O-diethyl-O[3,5,6-trichloro-2-
97 pyridinyl] phosphate, 99%), diazinon (O,O-diethyl O-2-isopropyl-6-
98 methylpyridimidinyl phosphorothioate, 97.7%), diazinon-oxon (O,OdiethylO-2-
99 isopropyl-6-methylpyridimidinyl phosphate, 95.8%) were obtained from Chem
100 Service (Pennsylvania, USA). Empty polypropylene SPE tubes (1 mL) with
101 polyethylene frits (1 /16', 20 µm porosity) were obtained from Supelco (Bellefonte,
102 USA). All solvents used (acetonitrile (ACN), methanol (MeOH), and acetic acid
103 (AcOH)) were of HPLC grade, and they were purchased from VWR Chemicals
104 (Barcelona, Spain).

105

106 *2.2. Instrumentation*

107 The morphology of the materials was characterized with a scanning electron
108 microscope S-4800 (Hitachi, Ibaraki, Japan) equipped with a field emission gun, and
109 an EMIP 3.0 image data acquisition system. For these measurements, the materials
110 were sputtered-coated with a thin layer Au/Pd. Nitrogen adsorption-desorption
111 isotherms were obtained at 77 K on a Micromeritics (Norcross, GA, USA) ASAP-
112 2020 automated instrument. Specific surface areas were evaluated using the Brunauer-
113 Emmett-Teller (BET) method and the pore size distribution was calculated using the
114 Barrett–Joyner–Halenda (BJH) method. Attenuated total reflection FT-IR spectra of

115 powdered materials were obtained with a Spectrum Two FT-IR Spectrometer (Perkin
116 Elmer, MA, USA). Spectra were accomplished from 4500 to 100 cm^{-1} .
117 The chromatographic determination of the analytes was conducted in HPLC system
118 from Agilent technology (1200 series (Waldbronn, Germany) provided with a
119 quaternary pump, a degasser, a thermostated column compartment, an automatic
120 sampler and a UV-vis diode array detector. The separation was performed on a
121 Phenomenex C18 column (250×4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size). Diazinon and diazinon-
122 oxon were monitored at 250 nm, whereas the chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-oxon were
123 detected at 290 nm. The injection volume was 20 μL , the flow rate was 1 mL min^{-1}
124 and the column temperature, 40°C. An isocratic elution method was employed using as
125 mobile phase a mixture of MeOH/H₂O containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid, 80/20, v/v.

126

127 *2.3. Preparation of MIPs*

128 Several imprinted polymers were prepared using different pesticides as template
129 molecules: chlorpyrifos (MIP 1), chlorpyrifos oxon (MIP 2), diazinon (MIP 3) and
130 diazinon-oxon (MIP 4). The synthesis of MIPs was prepared with a constant ratio of
131 template/monomer/crosslinker (1:4:20). Briefly, 0.25 mmol of template and 1 mmol of
132 MAA as the functional monomer were dissolved in ACN in a glass vial and it was
133 ultrasonically homogenized for 10 min. Then, 5 mmol of crosslinker EGDMA and 10
134 mg of initiator AIBN were added to the mixture and purged with nitrogen stream for
135 10 min. The mixture was kept in a silicon bath (60 °C) for 18 h. Then, the material
136 was washed with a large volume of ACN and MeOH to remove the template, dried
137 and grinded (< 50 μm). Non-imprinted polymer (NIP) was also prepared following the
138 aforementioned protocol for MIP synthesis without template.

139

140 *2.4. MIP-SPE protocol*

141 To evaluate the applicability of the synthesized materials, 40 mg of each polymer
142 (MIP or NIP) were packed between two frits into 1.0 mL empty SPE cartridge. The
143 cartridge was conditioned and equilibrated with MeOH (3 mL) and water (3 mL).
144 Then, 50.00 mL of a multicomponent standard aqueous solution ($1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) was
145 percolated through the SPE cartridge. At that point, the material was washed with
146 water (2 mL) and dried for 5 minutes with air stream. Afterwards, the retained analytes
147 were eluted with 1.5 mL of MeOH/acetic acid mixture (95/5, v/v). All the resulting
148 fractions were collected and properly diluted or evaporated and redissolved before
149 their HPLC-UV analysis.

150

151 *2.5. Sample preparation*

152 Water samples from different sources were collected. Sampling sites along with their
153 coordinates are indicated as follows. Thus, tap water was collected from Burjassot city
154 ($39^{\circ}30'27.1''\text{N } 0^{\circ}25'10.3''\text{W}$) in the Valencian Community, Spain. The river water
155 sample in Turia River basin ($39^{\circ}29'33.6''\text{N } 0^{\circ}27'07.4''\text{W}$) and sewage water were
156 collected from the effluent of the municipal wastewater treatment plant of Gandía
157 ($38^{\circ}58'50.4''\text{N } 0^{\circ}09'43.3''\text{W}$) in province of Valencia. These samples were collected in
158 amber glass bottles and immediately transported to the laboratory and stored in amber
159 glass flasks at -4°C until analysis. Once samples were obtained, they were filtered
160 through membranes ($0.22 \mu\text{m}$ porosity) and loaded through MIP cartridge as described
161 above. Since these samples did not show detectable levels of OPPs and their oxon
162 forms, they were spiked with different levels of pollutants.

163

164 **3. Results and discussion**

165 *3.1. Preliminary studies*

166 In the synthesis process of MIPs, the choice of several constituents is a key aspect to
167 achieve the optimal MIPs' preparation with proper selectivity against to the NIP. In
168 this sense, the recognition sites are influenced by the selection of proper template and
169 functional monomer. Most MIPs synthesized for OPPs [16] have commonly employed
170 MAA as functional monomer and EDGMA as crosslinker. Following these studies,
171 several mixtures of different templates, MAA, EGDMA (using the most common ratio
172 1/4/20 template/monomer/cross-linker) and ACN porogen were tested. In this work,
173 the four targeted compounds (chlorpyrifos, chlorpyrifos oxon, diazinon and diazinon
174 oxon) were used as template to prepare the corresponding polymers (MIP1, MIP2,
175 MIP3 and MIP4, respectively). To study the extraction performance of these MIPs
176 towards the four target compounds, a solution containing ($1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) of each OPP was
177 applied to each material and also with the NIP (Fig. 1). As it can be seen, MIP 3
178 showed the highest recovery values of OPPs (59.6-104.3%) compared to other MIPs.
179 Additionally, the imprinting factors (IF) of this MIP, defined as the ratio between
180 recoveries on MIP and on NIP (see Table S1) were evaluated. The results showed that
181 only MIP 3 gave three IF values higher than 1.2 for three of the four target
182 compounds. Therefore, MIP 3 was chosen for further experiments.

183

184 *3.2. Characterization and evaluation of selected MIP*

185 Once the couple of polymers was selected, MIP3 and its corresponding NIP, they were
186 morphological and chemical characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM),
187 nitrogen adsorption/desorption and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR).
188 SEM micrographs (Fig. 2) of both materials showed that the particles form

189 agglomerated structures with a rough surface with irregular order. In the case of NIP
190 (Fig. 2B), lower pores and particles with undefined shapes were evidenced. As it can
191 be seen, no significant differences were found in the sizes of MIP and NIP particles.
192 Nitrogen adsorption-desorption measurements were also performed in order to
193 confirm the formation of selective cavities. As shown in Fig. S1, for both materials, a
194 microporous behavior was observed at relatively lower partial pressures ($P/P_0 < 0.1$).
195 Also, at higher relative pressures ($P/P_0 \sim 0.5$), a second step was evidenced, which
196 corresponds to the filling of the large pores (in the meso-macro range) typically found
197 in these organic polymers. Despite of the similarity of curves, the nitrogen amount
198 absorbed in the first step was higher in the MIP isotherm (see Fig. S1), which can be
199 attributed to the presence of microporous cavities. Furthermore, MIP showed larger
200 specific surface area ($129.6 \pm 0.8 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) than NIP ($73.2 \pm 0.4 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and the pore
201 diameter (in the range $P/P_0 < 0.15$) was larger for the MIP than for the corresponding
202 NIP (0.72 and 0.57 nm for MIP and NIP, respectively). From these results, it can be
203 confirmed that the formation of selective cavities in the MIP were successfully
204 produced and they are expected to enhance its extraction performance.

205 On the other hand, FT-IR spectra of monomer (MAA) and the prepared polymers
206 (MIP3 and NIP) were done (see Fig. S2). The FT-IR spectrum of MAA showed a
207 broad peak at 2929 cm^{-1} that indicated the presence of C–H stretching vibrations of
208 MAA. Also, a band located close to 1700 cm^{-1} was assigned to carboxylic acid group,
209 whereas the peak at 1631 cm^{-1} was attributed to C=C stretching. After polymerization,
210 this latter peak decreased which was evident from MAA monomer the reaction. From
211 the FTIR spectra of MIP3 and NIP, both showed the –C=O stretching frequency at
212 1720 cm^{-1} approx., and another absorption peak (stretching vibration of C–H bonds in
213 methyl groups at approx. 2960 cm^{-1}), thus indicating similarity of polymer

214 composition and their structure. On the other hand, a broad absorption band at *ca.*
215 3000 cm^{-1} in the MIP corresponded to several overlapped peaks of infrared absorption
216 such as the stretching vibration of O–H bonds of MAA molecules (functional
217 monomer) and the hydrogen bonding interactions between template (diazinon) and
218 MAA. However, for the NIP, a weaker absorption peak around 3000 cm^{-1} was found
219 due to the lack of hydrogen bonding interaction between diazinon and MAA.

220

221 *3.3. Optimization of MIP-SPE protocol*

222 In order to enhance the selectivity of MIP3 versus NIP as well as the quantitative
223 recoveries of target analytes, the effect of different experimental factors (washing
224 solvent and composition and/or volume of eluting solvent) on extraction efficiency
225 were evaluated.

226 The choice of a washing solvent is a critical step in the extraction procedure in order to
227 ensure a selective extraction of analytes by removing unwanted matrix interferences.

228 In general, the porogenic solvent is commonly used as the washing solvent [29]. For
229 that reason, ACN and water-ACN mixtures were evaluated (Table 1). As it can be
230 seen, the highest recovery (94-100%) and the best imprinting factors (1.4-2.2) were
231 found in method 7. Therefore, the optimal composition was as follows: 2 mL water
232 (adjusted to pH 9.0, 50 mM phosphate)/ACN (85/15, v/v). This working pH for the
233 washing step did not affect significantly to the hydrogen-bonding interaction (retention
234 between the analytes and the MIP [30]).

235 Then, the effect of eluting solvent was considered. In this study, MeOH was selected as
236 the eluting solvent due to its strong hydrogen bond interactions with the analytes,
237 which may favor an efficient elution. The addition of a small percentage of acetic acid
238 (between 1 and 5%) in the aqueous methanolic mixture was also tested. In this case, an

239 elution volume of 2 mL was selected. As shown in Fig. 3, higher amounts of MeOH
240 and acetic acid in the elution composition (95:05 MeOH:AcOH, v/v) increased the
241 recovery of analytes, particularly for chlorpyrifos (from 66.5 to 91.0 %). This might
242 have been because of acetic acid disrupts hydrogen bonding between analytes and
243 MAA, being much easier the analytes desorption by MeOH [30]. Next, the effect of
244 different eluent volumes was investigated from 1 to 3 mL, giving 1.5 mL the best
245 elution volume, and it was selected for the elution step. In order to improve the
246 preconcentration factor of the proposed method, the possibility of evaporating the
247 elution extract was investigated. In this sense, the elution fraction was evaporated
248 under nitrogen stream and reconstituted in 100-200 μ L of mobile phase. Results
249 showed that after evaporation of the solvent and its redissolution with 150 μ L,
250 satisfactory recovery values (> 90 % for all analytes with lower RSD than 5%) were
251 obtained, which allow the use of a reconstitution step.

252 Next, the breakthrough volume was studied (see Fig. S3) using the optimized washing
253 and elution step, which indicates the maximum sample volume that can be loaded in
254 this SPE sorbent with these conditions. For this purpose, different amounts from 2 to
255 75 mL were tested, containing all of them 2 μ g of each OPP. Considering the
256 reconstitution step and the maximum sample volume obtained with ≥ 80 % recoveries
257 (50 mL), the enrichment factor of the method was evaluated, and they were in the
258 range from 233 to 316.

259 The loading capacity of the imprinted sorbent was also evaluated. For this purpose,
260 samples of water (50 mL) (spiked with a mixture containing increasing amounts of all
261 target compounds) were percolated through the MIP cartridge and the recovery yields
262 were measured (see Fig. S4). The adsorption capacity of the MIP referred to one
263 analyte was determined to be 2 μ g of OPP per mg sorbent with recoveries upper than

264 80%. This value is higher than that reported in the literature for this type of
265 compounds [16].

266 The reusability of the MIP3 as SPE sorbent was estimated using a standard solution of
267 $1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of each pollutant. The imprinted polymer can be reused at least 50 times
268 without loss of affinity towards the target molecules (recoveries $> 95\%$). This fact
269 allows the present method to be competitive and economically feasible towards other
270 MIPs and commercial sorbents.

271

272 *3.4. Application to water samples*

273 The optimized MIP-SPE protocol was validated with respect to linearity and
274 sensitivity. The corresponding calibration graphs were constructed by extracting
275 working aqueous standards containing the four analytes at different concentrations
276 ($0.5\text{-}5,000 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$). Good linearity was found in the working range with coefficient of
277 correlations above 0.997. The LODs of the MIP-SPE method, determined at a signal to
278 noise ratio of 3 ($S/N = 3$), were ranged from 0.07 to $0.12 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The LOQs,
279 determined at a signal-to-noise ratio of 10 ($S/N = 10$), were comprised between 0.23
280 and $0.41 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

281 To study the effectiveness of the developed MIP-SPE method, it was applied to real
282 water samples to analyze these target analytes (or OPPs and their oxon derivatives). It
283 was found that none of the target pesticides were detected in any of the real water
284 samples analyzed. Thus, in order to determine the accuracy of the method, the real
285 samples were spiked with the four pesticides (simultaneously) at $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and the
286 resulting extraction performances were evaluated (see Table 2). The recoveries
287 obtained for these spiked samples ranged from 79 ± 6 to $104 \pm 3 \%$. These results
288 revealed that the MIP had suitable affinity for the target pesticides in aqueous solution,

289 thus indicating the suitability of the method for analysis of real environmental water
290 samples. As example, Figure 4 shows the chromatograms from the unspiked river
291 sample and spiked river water sample with pollutants. As it can be seen, an enrichment
292 factor of analytes without an enhancement of matrix interferences was evidenced,
293 which showed the effectiveness of the MIP to be used as clean-up and
294 preconcentration purposes.

295

296 3.5. Comparison with other methods

297 The developed method was compared with other recent methods studies reported in
298 the literature for the determination of OPPs in environmental water samples (Table 3).
299 Concerning the recoveries, the values described here were similar to those reported in
300 the literature [33, 34] and quite superior than others [31, 35, 36, 37]. Regarding the
301 LODs, our values (using accessible UV-detector) were higher than other methods (see
302 Table 3), which used sophisticated and high sensitive techniques (*e.g.* HPLC- or
303 UPLC-MS-MS) [31, 37]. Some advantages of the synthesized MIP phase were: i) the
304 large reusability (more than 50 re-uses with no significant losses) compared to the
305 commercial sorbents (Oasis HLB and C18), which are relatively expensive and
306 designed for single use [31, 35, 36, 37]; ii) the less amount required (40 mg) in
307 comparison to other reported phases (200 mg [31, 36] and 500 mg [33, 35, 37]); and
308 iii) shorter synthesis process (18 h) than other non-commercial sorbents reported (36.1
309 h and 27 h for a MIP [33] and UVM-7 [34] materials, respectively). Besides, the small
310 volume of organic solvent needed to desorb quantitatively the analytes (1.5 mL) was
311 below than other reported works (10 mL in [31, 36, 37]), representing an advance in
312 the reduction of hazardous organic solvents. All these features combined with the
313 cheap preparation of the MIP-material undoubtedly make the present protocol

314 competent to be applied for determination of these pollutants in environmental
315 matrices. In any case, to our knowledge, this is the first time that a MIP-SPE-HPLC-
316 UV method is able to determine simultaneously the OPPs and their more toxic oxon
317 metabolites in water samples.

318

319 **4. Conclusions**

320 In this work, a selective MIP-SPE sorbent was synthesized by bulk polymerization and
321 applied to the extraction of chlorpyrifos, diazinon and their corresponding oxon forms
322 in water samples, followed by HPLC-UV analysis. Several imprinted polymers were
323 firstly synthesized using different pesticides as template molecules in order to find the
324 MIP that could extract selectively all the considered analytes. From this study, the
325 prepared MIP with diazinon as a template molecule showed the best recognition
326 ability giving a remarkable affinity to these compounds. The MIP potential was
327 demonstrated by its application to different types of environmental aqueous samples.
328 The MIP-SPE method presents enhanced advantages respect previously reported
329 works such as cost-effective and selectivity towards analytes with different polarities
330 (organophosphorus pesticides and their oxon derivatives). Additionally, the protocol
331 developed here also provided satisfactory LODs using common equipment accessible
332 in most analytical laboratories. Consequently, it represents a promising alternative for
333 monitoring chlorpyrifos, diazinon and their oxon forms from water samples.

334

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342

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344 **References**

- 345 [1] D. Sharma, A. Nagpal, Y.B. Pakade, J.K. Katnoria, Analytical methods for
346 estimation of organophosphorus pesticide residues in fruits and vegetables: a review.
347 *Talanta* 82 (2010) 1077–1089. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2010.06.043>.
- 348 [2] M. Marsin Sanagi, S. Salleh, W. Aini Wan Ibrahim, A. Abu Naim, D. Hermawan,
349 M. Miskam, I. Hussain, H. Y. Aboul-Enein, Molecularly imprinted polymer solid-
350 phase extraction for the analysis of organophosphorus pesticides in fruit samples. *J.*
351 *Food Comp. Anal.* 32 (2013) 155-161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2013.09.001>
- 352 [3] W. Li, R. Wu, J. Duan, C. P. Saint, J. van Leeuwen, Impact of prechlorination on
353 organophosphorus pesticides during drinking water treatment: Removal and
354 transformation to toxic oxon byproducts. *Water Res.* 105 (2016) 1-10.
355 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.08.052>
- 356 [4] A. Kamel, C Byrne, C. Vigob, J. Ferrario, C. Stafford, G. Verdin, F. Siegelman, S.
357 Knizner, J. Hetrick, Oxidation of selected organophosphate pesticides during
358 chlorination of simulated drinking water. *Water Res.* 43 (2009) 522–534.
359 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2008.10.038>
- 360 [5] E. Carazo, G Pérez, M. Perez, C. Chinchilla, J. Chin, P. Aguilar, M. Alpízar, M.
361 Masís, C. Rodríguez, Z. Vryzas, Pesticide monitoring and ecotoxicological risk
362 assessment in surface water bodies and sediments of a tropical agro-ecosystem.
363 *Environ. Pollut.* 241(2018) 800-809. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2018.06.020>
- 364 [6] D. Harshit, K. Charmy, P. Nrupesh, Organophosphorus pesticides determination by
365 novel HPLC and spectrophotometric method. *Food Chem.* 230 (2017) 448-453.
366 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2017.03.083>
- 367 [7] F. Donato, N. Bandeira, G. Dos-Santos, O. Prestes, M. Adaime, R. Zanella,
368 Evaluation of the rotating disk sorptive extraction technique with polymeric sorbent

369 for multiresidue determination of pesticides in water by ultra-high-performance liquid
370 chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry. *J. Chromatogr. A* 1516 (2017) 54-66.
371 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2017.08.025>

372 [8] M. Tankiewicz, J. Fenik, M. Biziuk, Determination of organophosphorus and
373 organonitrogen pesticides in water samples. *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 29
374 (2010)1050–1063. doi:10.1016/j.trac.2010.05.008.

375 [9] Y.B. Pakade, D.K. Tewary, Development and applications of single-drop
376 microextraction for pesticide residue analysis: A review. *J. Sep. Sci.* 33 (2010) 3683–
377 3691. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jssc.201000331>

378 [10] A. M. Carro, S. Fernández, I. Racamonde, D. García-Rodríguez, P. González, R.
379 A. Lorenzo, Dispersive liquid–liquid microextraction coupled with programmed
380 temperature vaporization-large volume injection-gas chromatography–tandem mass
381 spectrometry for multiclass pesticides in water. *J. of Chromatogr. A* 1253 (2012) 134-
382 143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2012.06.089>

383 [11] M.Tankiewicz, J. Fenik, M. Biziuk, Solventless and solvent-minimized sample
384 preparation techniques for determining currently used pesticides in water samples: A
385 review. *Talanta* 86 (2011) 8-22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2011.08.056>

386 [12] C. Basheer, A. Ali Alnedhary, B.S. Madhava Rao, H. KeeLee, Determination of
387 organophosphorous pesticides in wastewater samples using binary-solvent liquid-
388 phase microextraction and solid-phase microextraction: A comparative study. *Anal.*
389 *Chim. Acta* 605 (2007) 147-152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2007.10.006>

390 [13] M. Reza Hadjmohammadi, M. Peyrovi, P. Biparva, Comparison of C18 silica and
391 multi-walled carbon nanotubes as the adsorbents for the solid-phase extraction of
392 Chlorpyrifos and Phosalone in water samples using HPLC. *J. Sep. Sci.* 33 (2010)
393 1044-1051. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jssc.200900494>

- 394 [14] P. Wang, M. Luo, D. Liu, J. Zhan, X. Liu, F. Wang, Z. Zhou, Application of a
395 magnetic graphene nanocomposite for organophosphorus pesticide extraction in
396 environmental water samples. *J. Chromatogr. A* 1535 (2018) 9 -16.
397 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2018.01.003>
- 398 [15] V. Pichon, N. Delaunay, A. Combès, Sample preparation using molecularly
399 imprinted polymers. *Anal. Chem.* 92 (2020) 16-33.
400 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.9b04816>
- 401 [16] S. Boulanouar, A. Combès, S. Mezzache, V. Pichon, Synthesis and application of
402 molecularly imprinted polymers for the selective extraction of organophosphorus
403 pesticides from vegetable oils. *J. Chromatogr. A* 1513 (2017) 59-68.
404 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2017.07.067>
- 405 [17] X. Zhu, J. Yang, Q. Su, J. Cai, Y. Gao, Selective solid-phase extraction using
406 molecularly imprinted polymer for the analysis of polar organophosphorus pesticides
407 in water and soil samples. *J. Chromatogr.* 1092 (2005) 161–169.
408 <https://doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2005.07.037>.
- 409 [18] S. Boulanouar, S. Mezzache, A. Combès, V. Pichon, Molecularly imprinted
410 polymers for the determination of organophosphorus pesticides in complex samples.
411 *Talanta* 176 (2018) 465-478. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2017.08.067>
- 412 [19] L.A. Pereira, S. Rath, Molecularly imprinted solid-phase extraction for the
413 determination of fenitrothion in tomatoes. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 393 (2008) 1063–
414 1072. <https://doi:10.1007/s00216-008-2511-0>.
- 415 [20] Shen, Zhong-Lan, D. Yuan, Q.-D. SU, H. Zhang, J. Wang, J.-H. Zhu, Y.-M. Liu,
416 Selective solid-phase extraction using molecularly imprinted polymer for analysis of
417 methamidophos in water and soil samples. *Biosci. Biotech. Bioch.* 75 (2011) 473–
418 479. <https://doi:10.1271/bbb.100668>.

419 [21] J.-J. Du, R.-X. Gao, H. Yu, X.-J. Li, H. Mu, Selective extraction of dimethoate
420 from cucumber samples by use of molecularly imprinted microspheres. *J. Pharm.*
421 *Anal.* 5 (2015) 200–206. <https://doi:10.1016/j.jpha.2014.10.004>

422 [22] S. Xu, C. Guo, Y. Li, Z. Yu, C. Wei, Y. Tang, Methyl parathion imprinted
423 polymer nanoshell coated on the magnetic nanocore for selective recognition and fast
424 adsorption and separation in soils. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 264 (2014) 34–41. <https://doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2013.10.060>.

426 [23] Q. Lu, X. Chen, L. Nie, J. Luo, H. Jiang, L. Chen, Q. Hu, S. Du, Z. Zhang,
427 Tuning of the vinyl groups' spacing at surface of modified silica in preparation of high
428 density imprinted layer-coated silica nanoparticles: A dispersive solid-phase extraction
429 materials for chlorpyrifos. *Talanta* 81 (2010) 959–966. <https://doi:10.1016/j.talanta.2010.01.044>.

431 [24] F.X. Liang, X.L. Zhu, J. Yang, Q.D. Su, Accelerated solvent extraction and
432 matrix solid phase dispersion using molecularly imprinted polymer for the analysis of
433 monocrotophos in soil. *Asian J. Chem.* 20 (2008) 3954–3960.

434 [25] X. Wang, X. Qiao, Y. Ma, T. Zhao, Z. Xu, Simultaneous determination of nine
435 trace organophosphorous pesticide residues in fruit samples using molecularly
436 imprinted matrix solid-phase dispersion followed by gas chromatography. *J. Agric.*
437 *Food Chem.* 61 (2013) 3821–3827. <https://doi:10.1021/jf400269q>.

438 [26] X. Zhu, J. Cai, J. Yang, Q. Su, Y. Gao, Films coated with molecular imprinted
439 polymers for the selective stir bar sorption extraction of monocrotophos, *J.*
440 *Chromatogr. A* 1131 (2006) 37–44. <https://doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2006.07.041>.

441 [27] Y.-L. Wang, Y.-L. Gao, P.-P. Wang, H. Shang, S.-Y. Pan, X.-J. Li, Sol–gel
442 molecularly imprinted polymer for selective solid phase microextraction of

443 organophosphorous pesticides. *Talanta*. 115 (2013) 920–927. [https://](https://doi:10.1016/j.talanta.2013.06.056)
444 doi:10.1016/j.talanta.2013.06.056.

445 [28] J.-W. Li, Y.-L. Wang, S. Yan, X.-J. Li, S.-Y. Pan, Molecularly imprinted
446 calixarene fiber for solid-phase microextraction of four organophosphorous pesticides
447 in fruits. *Food Chem.* 192 (2016) 260–267. [https://](https://doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2015.07.018)
448 doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2015.07.018.

449 [29] A. Binsalom, I.Chianella, K. Campbell, M. Zourob, Development of solid-phase
450 extraction using molecularly imprinted polymer for the analysis of organophosphorus
451 pesticides-(chlorpyrifos) in aqueous solution. *J. Chromatogr. Sep. Sci.* 7 (2016) 1-6.
452 <https://doi.org/10.4172/2157-7064.1000340>

453 [30] M.M. Sanagi, S. Salleh, W.A.W. Ibrahim, A.A. Naim, D. Hermawan, M.
454 Miskam, I. Hussain, H.Y. Aboul-Enein, Molecularly imprinted polymer solid-phase
455 extraction for the analysis of organophosphorus pesticides in fruit samples. *J. Food*
456 *Comp. Anal.* 32 (2013) 155–161. [https:// doi: 10.1016/j.jfca.2013.09.001](https://doi:10.1016/j.jfca.2013.09.001).

457 [31] A.C. Charalampous, G.E. Miliadis, M.A. Koupparis, A new multiresidue method
458 for the determination of multiclass pesticides, degradation products and PCBs in wáter
459 using LC–MS/MS and GC–MS(n)systems, *Int. J. Environ. An. Ch.* 95 (2015) 1283–
460 1298. [https:// doi:10.1080/03067319.2015.1100723](https://doi:10.1080/03067319.2015.1100723).

461 [32] M.D. Gil García, S. Dahane, F.M. Arrabal-Campos, M.M. SocíasViciano, M.A.
462 García, I. Fernández, M. Martínez Galera, MCM-41 as novel solid phase sorbent for
463 the pre-concentration of pesticides in environmental waters and determination by
464 microflow liquid chromatography-quadrupole linear ion trap mass spectrometry,
465 *Microchem. J.* 134 (2017) 181–190. <https://doi:10.1016/j.microc.2017.06.008>.

466 [33] M.E. Khalifa, I.M.M. Kenawy, Y.G. Abou El-Reash, A.B. Abdallah, Extractive
467 separation of profenofos as an organophosphorus insecticide from wastewater and

468 plant samples using molecular imprinted cellulose, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 5 (2017)
469 951 3447–3454. <https://doi:10.1016/j.jece.2017.07.012>.

470 [34] E. Pellicer-Castell, C. Belenguer-Sapiña, P. Amorós, Jamal El Haskouri, J.
471 Herrero-Martínez, A. Mauri-Aucejo, Study of silica-structured materials as sorbents
472 for organophosphorus pesticides determination in environmental water samples.
473 *Talanta* 189 (2018) 560-567. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2018.07.044>

474 [35] T.G. Schwanz, C.K. Carpilovsky, G.C.C. Weis, I.H. Costabeber, Validation of a
475 multiresidue method and estimation of measurement uncertainty of pesticides 1081 in
476 drinking water using gas chromatography–mass spectrometry and liquid
477 chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1585 (2019) 10–18.
478 1084 <https://doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2018.11.058>.

479 [36] J. Casado, D. Santillo, P. Johnston, Multi-residue analysis of pesticides in Surface
480 water by liquid chromatography quadrupole-Orbitrap high resolution tandem mass
481 spectrometry. *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1024 (2018) 1–17.
482 <https://doi:10.1016/j.aca.2018.04.026>.

483 [37] M. Xu, H. Huang, N. Li, F. Li, D. Wang, Q. Luo, Occurrence and ecological risk
484 of pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs) and pesticides in typical
485 Surface watersheds, China. *Ecotox. Environ. Safe.* 175 (2019) 289–298.
486 <https://doi:10.1016/j.ecoenv.2019.01.131>.

487 **Figure captions**

488

489 **Figure 1.** Recovery of pesticides in the elution fraction obtained on four MIP and NIP
490 synthesized. SPE conditions given in the text. Polymerization mixture composition is
491 given in Experimental part. (n=3)

492

493 **Figure 2.** SEM micrographs of (A) MIP3 and (B) NIP measured at 35,000 \times .

494

495 **Figure 3.** Influence of the elution solvent composition on the recovery of four
496 compounds investigated. Conditions: sample volume, 2 mL; sorbent amount, 40 mg;
497 eluent volume, 2 mL; the test mixture used was 1 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for each analyte.

498

499 **Figure 4.** LC-UV chromatograms of a spiked river water sample before (grey line)
500 and after (black line) MIP-SPE treatment. Peak identification: (1) Diazinon-oxon; (2)
501 Chlorpyrifos-oxon; (3) Diazinon; (4) Chlorpyrifos. Chromatographic conditions and
502 extraction protocol are described in Sections 2.2 and 2.4, respectively.